

D6.5 (M24) - Report on marine biodiversity resources (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

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Context

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, is operating molecular reference databases for salmon, salmon lice, and prokaryotes from the marine domain. This report, Deliverable 6.5, concerns the activities and operation of these databases in terms of technical and content updates by Work Package 6 (WP6).

The SalmoBase (<https://salmobase.org>), LiceBase (<https://licebase.org>), and the microbial databases held in the Marine Metagenomics Portal (MMP, <https://mmp.sfb.uit.no>, hosting the databases MarRef, MarDB, SalDB, MarFun, and MarVirus) are central to ELIXIR₃ and the ELIXIR Norway Service Delivery Plan. These databases play crucial roles in advancing research within their respective domains, providing annotations encompassing functional assignment and taxonomic classification for the topics circumscribing lice genomics, salmonid genetics, and microbial communities in marine environments. The operation of these resources necessitates maintenance, upgrades, and expansion of reference data to provide up-to-date and available services for researchers in the domains and biodiversity at large.

Delivery

SalmoBase (by LG)

- **Technical updates:**

- Added support for multiple assemblies per species.
- Added support for multiple annotations per assembly (e.g. both NCBI and Ensembl annotations).
- Added filter for gene search: Search selected species, assembly, or annotation.
- Chromosome alias: Now possible to load tracks with alternative sequence names. Valid sequence IDs are. RefSeq, genbank, Ensembl or "sequence name". Aliases are also displayed when hovering the chromosome on the genome page.
- Gene page URL now uses geneIDs by default (NCBI gene ID or Ensembl gene ID). Gene annotations from earlier assemblies can be accessed by specifying the assembly with a parameter.
- Implemented a custom track configuration system for datasets.
- Many minor backend and UI fixes/improvements.
- **New content:**
 - New assemblies:
 - Atlantic salmon:
 - Ssal_v3.1
 - Ssal_Brian_v1.0
 - Ssal_ALTA
 - Rainbow trout:
 - USDA_OmykA_1.1
 - Coho salmon:
 - Okis_V2
 - Updated orthology data for new assemblies (gene trees, orthologs, synteny blocks).
 - Added comparative ortholog/paralog tracks.
 - Added comparative genome alignments for salmon and trout (within and between species).
 - AQUA-FAANG dataset (RNA-seq, ATAC-seq and CHIP-seq (four histone marks) of tissues and developing embryos in Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout):
 - All nf-core results are made available.
 - Trackhubs with all tracks from nf-core results.
 - ChromHMM chromatin state tracks.
 - Annotated robust ATAC-seq peak tracks.
 - Blacklists.

LiceBase (by MD)

- Technical updates of the hosting server environment.

- Performance updates of the database.
- Security updates of the web framework (Drupal 7).
- Prepared test environment for migration to Drupal 10 / Tripal 4.
- Prepared for moving the service to cloud infrastructure.
- Added RACE-PCR sequences for selected genes.

Marine Metagenomics Portal (by TK and BR)

- **Technical deliveries:**
 - The MMP is undergoing several upgrades, including the extension of a new database named MarVirus which holds manually curated records of marine viruses. Specifications for MarVirus have been defined using the attribute schemas of the ENA virus pathogen reporting standard checklist ([ERC000033](#)) and [MIGSVirus checklist](#). The final configuration went through a mapping process considering both checklists to ensure a non-redundant attribute specification for the MarVirus database. The attribute specifications schema itself is contained and available in the database:
 - [MarVirus attribute specifications](#)
 - The attribute implementation was conducted using the [contextual biodata framework \(CBF\)](#) hosted on [Sigma2/NIRD](#) for MarVirus:
 - [MarVirus instance of CBF](#)
 - The MarRef database has also received an update of its attribute specifications to improve readability, clarity, operation, and update efficiency. Similarly to MarVirus, the specification is contained within the database itself:
 - [MarRef attribute specifications](#)
- **Ongoing technical deliveries:**
 - In WP6 T6.5 there are ongoing preparations for storing contextual and sequence data related to the MMP services on [Sigma2/NIRD](#). This includes the complete and stable deployment of the CBF, the attribute specifications for CBF, contextual data contained in CBF, sequence data as assembly, gene, and protein for all MMP database services, and the storing and enabling of BLAST services.
 - The MMP service, including CBF, is undergoing an upgrade which will impact the system hosting. The upgrade is being built on a foundation consisting of [Supabase](#) and [Next.js](#).
 - Some of the ongoing work is to move the CBF instances of databases listed in the MMP from their hosting service at UiT Azure servers to NIRD.

- The CBF instance of MarVirus is established at NIRD, but has encountered issues with instability regarding the [LSlogin](#) component and is under revision.
 - The implementation of MarVirus as a usable database for external users of the MMP is still work in progress.
 - [MMP MarVirus](#)
- One of the analytic components connected to the MMP databases, the AutoGet tool for genome quality and taxonomy analysis, has been rebuilt as an OS-independent .Net C# library. The purpose of rebuilding AutoGet is to improve scalability and flexibility when mass-processing genomic records for systems like the MMP databases. The ongoing work in WP6 concerns the polishing and deployment of the AutoGet system in connection with the MMP. Once sufficiently tested the AutoGet will be published as a NuGet package. Both the old and the rebuilt versions of AutoGet are kept in their respective [GitLab](#) and [GitHub ELIXIR Norway](#) repositories.
- **Content updates and curation deliveries:**
 - The MarRef database has received contextual data updates with the addition of 146 manually curated records from the INSDC. These have been added to the MarRef, complete with the [evidence and conclusion ontology \(ECO\)](#) documenting curated values.
 - [MarRef at MMP](#)
 - The complete contextual dataset of MarRef has additionally been revised in terms of consistency and accuracy as well as the deprecation of records without clear provenance of marine origin, or removed by INSDC.
 - The first version of MarVirus is completed in terms of curation, with its initial dataset ready for implementation in the MMP. Viral records of sequences from [NCBI Virus](#) have been filtered for marine origin and curated similarly to MarRef to create this first version of the MarVirus database. This resulted in 115 virus records enriched with ontologies to project structured information previously locked in the literature. These were implemented in the CBF instance deployed for MarVirus on NIRD.
 - [MarVirus instance of CBF](#)
- **Ongoing content updates and curation deliveries:**
 - The curation of MarDB and SalDB for MMP is expected to result in approximately 7000 additional records for these databases. This dataset is the complement of records not qualified as reference data for MarRef.
 - Once the databases of the MMP are updated the next set of marine data published in the INSDC will be engaged to initiate the next update round for the MAR databases. This will be reported in the M48 report on task 6.5.

Outcomes

- The SalmoBase, LiceBase, and the MAR database are open resources available for the research communities at large, and significant for the interest of salmon research, biodiversity, and the marine domain. Maintaining, prolonging, and extending these services with updated content and functionality benefits research by setting the standard for hosting reference data in these domains. Furthermore, these services inspire reliable resources for updated molecular knowledge and express unique potential to assist researchers in discovering data beneficial for their projects.
- Maintainers of the services should strive to keep the databases updated and accessible for the research communities.
- Moving services, like the MMP and related databases, to NIRD synergizes the resources under ELIXIR Norway with the aim of improving service stability and reliability. This effect further benefits external scientists of these services as well as the maintainers at a technical level.
- The rewriting of AutoGet in .NET C# has expanded its capabilities by improving scalability and flexibility for use in other projects. This upgrade is particularly useful for databases requiring a scalable tool pipeline to perform repetitive and consistent data analysis on the backend. Moreover, AutoGet can now leverage API services to collect information and write analysis data into database solutions like the CBF.